

**Parental Differentiation of Self and Student Adjustment Patterns:
An Identification and Response Framework for School Counseling**

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Abstract

In this article, we bridge research and school counseling practice by applying Bowen family systems theory and differentiation of self (DoS) to support students affected by parental separation or divorce. Parental separation is a prevalent family transition associated with increased student anxiety, somatic complaints, behavioral dysregulation, and academic disruption. School counselors are uniquely positioned to identify these concerns early, yet often lack a coherent, systems-informed framework for understanding how parental coping patterns shape student functioning. Drawing on empirical research, we synthesize the four DoS subscales and translate them into observable student indicators, developmentally appropriate counselor responses, and practical tools aligned with ethical school counseling practice. Mapping tables link parental emotional patterns to common school-based presentations and recommended interventions. A brief case vignette and a differentiation-informed professional development module illustrate real-time application within the scope of school counseling. Framing DoS as both a conceptual lens and a professional competency, this work positions the school as a stabilizing system and advances more ethically grounded, systemic school counseling practice for students navigating ongoing family stress.

Keywords: Bowen family systems, differentiation of self, parental separation, divorce, school counseling

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This article is an effort to equip Alabama's school counselors with practical, evidence-based strategies for supporting students affected by parental divorce or separation. It concludes with practice implications and recommendations for counselor training and supervision in school-based settings. To facilitate understanding of parental coping patterns that may impact children's school performance, we have integrated three conceptual anchors: Bowen's seminal family systems theory (Kerr & Bowen, 1988), his conceptualization of differentiation of self (DoS) and its four subscales (Skowron & Schmitt, 2003), and observable school-based outcomes.

Scope of the Problem and the School Counselor's Role

The increasing fluidity of family structures is a prevalent challenge, and nearly one-third of U.S. children experience parental divorce or separation before reaching adulthood (Johnston et al., 2025). In Alabama, a state with one of the nation's higher rates of parental divorce or separation (Westrick-Payne, 2025), this disruption amplifies local demands on educational systems, manifesting in students' heightened emotional distress (e.g., anxiety), withdrawal, and acting-out behaviors, alongside declines in academic engagement and grades (D'Onofrio & Emery, 2019). Children of divorce often grapple with emotionally charged family systems that feature inconsistent parenting practices and competing caregiver expectations resulting from divided households. This situation creates challenges that contribute to rising school-based mental health concerns and highlights the need for proactive support to mitigate long-term impacts on social-emotional development (Karhina et al., 2023; Kelly & Emery, 2003).

School counselors, given their role as advocates and collaborators who monitor behavioral shifts and attendance patterns, are pivotal in identifying students at risk from family disruptions (American School Counselor Association [ASCA], 2025; Savitz-Romer et al., 2021). In fact, a noted strength of the profession lies in maintaining a unified educator-counselor identity, which enables proactive responses that promote student wellness and effective school-based interventions (ASCA, 2021; Levy & Lemberger-Truelove, 2021). School counselors are uniquely qualified to help children build coping skills that promote resilience and adaptation to parental divorce or separation through timely identification and sustained support.

From a Bowenian perspective, divorce represents a restructuring of the family system, not a dissolution, as emotional processes, relational triangles, and intergenerational patterns continue in new configurations (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). Because systemic connections persist after separation, parental emotional reactivity, fusion, or post-separation cutoffs may continue to shape children's adjustment, either amplifying anxiety and behavioral challenges in school or supporting growth when higher differentiation fosters healthier co-parenting and boundary management (Moral et al., 2021; Titelman, 2014).

Given the well-documented impact of divorce on child adjustment (Amato, 2010; D'Onofrio & Emery, 2019; Kelly & Emery, 2003), targeted, theory-informed school-based support is essential. Grounded in Bowen family systems theory and DoS (Calatrava et al., 2022), the strategies that follow offer actionable guidance for fostering resilience, reducing anxiety-related barriers, and promoting healthy social-emotional development. We also offer concrete applications and recommendations for professional development.

Theoretical Foundations: Bowen Family Systems Theory and Differentiation of Self

Bowen family systems theory posits that individuals function within interconnected emotional systems; anxiety and emotional processes in one part of the system influence the entire unit (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). DoS, the capacity to maintain emotional autonomy while remaining connected in relationships, is central to this framework. Higher levels of DoS enable individuals to think, feel, and act independently without being overwhelmed by emotional reactivity or relational fusion, while lower levels are associated with amplified vulnerability to anxiety transmission across generations (Kerr & Bowen, 1988; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). Lower DoS in family systems heightens vulnerability to chronic anxiety and maladaptive child outcomes, underscoring the relevance of DoS in understanding adjustment during parental separation (Calatrava et al., 2022).

The Differentiation of Self Inventory-Revised (DSI-R; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003) operationalizes DoS through four key subscales, each capturing distinct patterns for managing anxiety and interpersonal boundaries (Skowron & Friedlander, 1998; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). Emotional reactivity (ER), the first subscale, reflects the intensity of emotional responses to stressors, with higher reactivity characterized by difficulty maintaining thoughtful responses under heightened affect (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). Parents with elevated ER during separation or divorce often exhibit inconsistent responses and fluctuating decision-making, contributing to an unstable emotional climate that can manifest in children as anxiety, somatic symptoms (e.g., headaches or stomachaches), and attention instability (Amato, 2010).

The second subscale is I-position (IP), which refers to the capacity to hold a clearly defined sense of self and express personal convictions while remaining connected to others. Lower IP may involve rigidity or over assertion to mask internal uncertainty (Kerr & Bowen,

1988). In post-separation dynamics, strained IP can lead to uneven communication patterns, placing pressure on children who may respond with over-responsibility, perfectionism, people-pleasing, or conflict avoidance (Skowron & Friedlander, 1998). Stronger I-position and lower emotional cutoff, reactivity, and fusion predicted better post-separation adjustment, highlighting pathways through which parental DoS shapes family emotional processes and children's adjustment and wellbeing (Moral et al., 2021).

Emotional cutoff (EC), the third subscale, describes efforts to manage anxiety through emotional distance, withdrawal, or avoidance of relational intimacy (Bowen, 1978). During divorce, EC may appear as parental emotional unavailability, which may cause students to display social withdrawal, muted affect, or reluctance to verbalize stress (Amato, 2010). Finally, fusion with others (FO) involves enmeshment or blurred boundaries, wherein individuals derive self-definition excessively from relationships (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). High fusion in separating parents often includes role-reversal or over-involvement, leading children to exhibit overcompliance, internalized anxiety, or challenges with independent decision-making (Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). These subscales interact dynamically, and profiles vary across individuals, while lower overall DoS heightens vulnerability to intergenerational emotional transmission.

Recent empirical studies further clarified the mechanisms through which parental DoS shapes children's adjustment. For instance, Mozas-Alonso et al. (2022) found that parents with higher differentiation reported more adaptive, inductive, and emotionally warm parenting practices, whereas those with lower levels exhibited greater emotional volatility and less consistent boundary-setting. Similarly, Klein et al. (2024) demonstrated that lower parental differentiation predicted increased externalizing behavior in children through need-frustrating parenting patterns that undermined autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Čepukienė and

Neophytou (2024) further showed that lower parental DoS transmitted intergenerationally via triangulation, impaired nuclear-family co-parenting and predicted greater psychological difficulties in children. These findings reinforced the relevance of DoS for school counselors, as students' anxiety, behavioral dysregulation, and academic difficulties may reflect parenting patterns that emerge from heightened family stress rather than isolated child-level pathology.

Empirical research supports DoS as a protective resource; higher levels predict lower perceived stress, greater resilience amid major stressors, improved emotional regulation, and better relationship stability, even during disruptive events like separation (Rodríguez-González et al., 2023; Süloğlu & Güler, 2021). For example, lower DoS has been associated with maladaptive metacognitions about worry and elevated trait anxiety, processes that contribute to rumination and attention difficulties observable in students (Álvarez-Hierro & Oliver, 2024). Recent evidence also linked parental separation to persistent academic penalties in middle and high school, outcomes that Bowenian theorists interpret as spillover from parental reactivity and fusion (Pesando & Stranges, 2024).

These dynamics offer school counselors a lens for recognizing how parental coping patterns influence student functioning, providing groundwork for targeted, resilience-building support (Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017). Collectively, this evidence demonstrates that parental separation functions less as a discrete event and more as a marker of cumulative stress exposure, particularly when accompanied by conflict, instability, or inconsistent caregiving. Accordingly, school counselors recognize the importance of assessing the students' broader stress context, not just family structure, when determining the timing and intensity of support.

Despite the explanatory strength of Bowen family systems theory, comparatively little attention has been given to systemic, school-based interventions that address intergenerational

anxiety transmission, leaving a gap in practical, theory-informed guidance for school counselors. The remainder of this article addresses this gap by offering family-systems-informed strategies, tools, and interventions designed to support students navigating parental separation and divorce. By equipping counselors with actionable approaches grounded in this theoretical foundation, we aim to enhance proactive identification, foster student resilience, and contribute to improved emotional and academic outcomes in school settings.

Applying Bowen Family Systems Theory in School Counseling Practice

Bowen family systems theory provides a robust lens for understanding children's emotional and behavioral responses to parental divorce, particularly through emotional reactivity, triangulation, and intergenerational anxiety transmission (Amato, 2010; Kerr & Bowen, 1988). Building on this theoretical and empirical foundation, we operationalize these insights through evidence-informed, school-based strategies that address students' anxiety and adjustment difficulties by identifying warning signs of distress, facilitating adaptive coping skills and differentiation, and strengthening emotional stability. These approaches align conceptually with trauma-informed practice and social-emotional learning frameworks and hold significant implications for counselor training, supervision, and school policy (Brown, 2025; Wells, 2022).

The four DoS subscales (emotional reactivity, I-position, emotional cutoff, and fusion with others) manifest in parental behaviors that often ripple into the school environment, presenting in students as anxiety, withdrawal, perfectionism, somatic complaints, or academic fluctuations (Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). The following sections and tables map these subscales to observable student indicators while outlining developmentally appropriate counselor responses that promote emotional regulation, strengthen executive functioning, and position the school as a consistent, structured source of student support.

Translating Theory Into Practice

To bridge Bowen family systems theory with school counseling practice, Table 1 translates the four DoS subscales into observable parental patterns during separation or divorce, common student presentations in the school environment, and recommended counselor responses. This mapping serves as a concise diagnostic and intervention guide for practitioners who may lack extensive training in Bowen theory, enabling real-time application to identify distress indicators, promote emotional regulation, and foster resilience (Kerr & Bowen, 1988; Skowron & Friedlander, 1998; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). By highlighting developmentally appropriate strategies aligned with established school counseling practices, the table supports proactive screening, individual or group interventions, supervision discussions, and professional development workshops (ASCA, 2025; Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017).

Table 1

Mapping DoS Subscales to Parental Patterns, Student Presentations, and School-Based Counselor Responses

Subscale	Common Parental Coping Patterns Post-Separation	Observable Student Presentations in School	Recommended Counselor Response
ER	High ER often involves inconsistent responses, elevated affect, and fluctuating decision-making.	Anxiety, somatic symptoms (e.g., headaches, stomachaches), and attention instability.	Emphasize co-regulation techniques, provide structured and predictable routines, and teach mindfulness or breathing exercises for emotional grounding.
IP	Strained IP may lead to decisive but uneven communication patterns with rigidity or over-assertion of personal views.	Over-responsibility, perfectionism, people-pleasing, and conflict avoidance.	Support autonomy through skill-building activities, such as goal-setting or assertive communication role-plays, to strengthen a clear sense of self.
EC	Cutoff manifests as parental withdrawal, reduced emotional availability, or avoidance of conflict discussion.	Social withdrawal, muted affect, or reluctance to verbalize stress.	Normalize emotional expression and provide expressive outlets; use expressive writing interventions to support articulation, emotional processing, and social-emotional regulation.

Subscale	Common Parental Coping Patterns Post-Separation	Observable Student Presentations in School	Recommended Counselor Response
FO	High fusion appears as blurred boundaries, enmeshment, or role-reversal (e.g., child as parental confidant).	Overcompliance, internalized anxiety, or difficulty with independent decision-making.	Teach boundary-setting skills, promote independent coping through problem-solving exercises, and leverage peer support groups for balanced relational experiences.

Note. ER = emotional reactivity, IP = I-position, EC = emotional cutoff, FO = fusion with others. Subscales were adapted from Kerr and Bowen (1988), Bowen (1978), and the DSI-R (Skowron & Friedlander, 1998; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). Observable student presentations are drawn from divorce impact research (Amato, 2010). Counselor responses reflect established school counseling practice (ASCA, 2025; Amos et al., 2025; Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017; Nasution & Darmayanti, 2025). Student presentations and counselor responses are illustrative; interventions should be individualized and culturally responsive.

Applied Case Illustration

The following case vignette illustrates Bowenian mechanisms, DoS, and a school counselor’s response within the limits of the school setting, written explicitly from a school counselor’s scope of practice and role, not a clinical or family therapy frame. The focus is academic functioning, somatic complaints, attention, and emotional regulation, not family restructuring, as school counselors should be vigilant about role boundaries when applying Bowen’s concepts (Paylo, 2011). All proposed interventions are brief, skill-based, developmentally appropriate, and prevention oriented, intentionally excluding family therapy, diagnosis, co-parenting mediation, and exploration of parental marital dynamics. Also, counselors should limit parental collaboration with communication boundaries and school-related coordination consistent with the ASCA National Model (ASCA, 2025; Wikoff & Rock, 2024).

Case Vignette

Maria is a seventh-grade student referred to the school counselor due to increasing somatic complaints, frequent visits to the nurse, and declining concentration in class. Her

teachers report that she appears vigilant, easily startled, and overly concerned about pleasing adults. During the intake meeting, she shares that her parents are in an ongoing, high-conflict separation marked by inconsistent schedules, frequent last-minute changes, and emotionally charged exchanges during custody transitions. Maria reports feeling responsible for “keeping the peace,” often acting as a messenger between parents and suppressing her own distress to avoid adding to family tension. From a Bowen family systems perspective, the counselor conceptualizes this presentation as emerging from intensified parental emotional reactivity and fusion, and Maria has been pulled into a stabilizing role within the family system (Titelman, 2014).

Prioritizing differentiation and emotional regulation over symptom reduction, the counselor designs interventions that strengthen Maria’s coping within the school setting. Initial sessions emphasize rapport-building, normalization of emotional responses to chronic conflict, and predictable structure to counteract instability at home. The counselor teaches brief grounding and breathing strategies to address somatic anxiety, while gently reinforcing that Maria is not responsible for managing adult relationships (Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017).

As sessions progress, the counselor introduces developmentally appropriate autonomy-building strategies, including identifying personal values, practicing assertive communication through role-play, and using journaling prompts to externalize emotions (Amos et al., 2025; Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017; Nasution & Darmayanti, 2025). With parental consent, the counselor collaborates with caregivers to establish clearer communication boundaries with Maria and to reduce triangulation during school-related exchanges. Over time, Maria demonstrates improved emotional awareness, reduced somatic complaints, and greater confidence expressing

needs without excessive self-blame, reflecting the school’s capacity to support emotional growth and adaptive coping amid ongoing family stress (Kerr & Bowen, 1988).

Translating the Vignette Into Practice

Table 2 maps the proposed counselor actions in the vignette to the four DoS subscales operationalized in Table 1 (Kerr & Bowen, 1988; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003).

Table 2

Mapping DoS Subscales to School Counseling Interventions

Subscale	Vignette Indicators	Counselor Actions	Theoretical Link
ER	Student presents with somatic complaints, vigilance, startle response, and attention instability linked to parental volatility and inconsistent routines.	Establishes predictable session structure to counteract family instability. Teaches brief grounding/breathing exercises to reduce physiological arousal. Normalizes emotional responses to chronic conflict, reducing shame-driven reactivity.	Directly targets elevated ER by strengthening regulation and co-regulation capacities within the school environment, consistent with Bowen’s emphasis on managing affect while acknowledging ongoing stressors.
IP	Student exhibits people-pleasing, over-responsibility, and reluctance to assert personal needs.	Reinforces that the student is not responsible for managing parental relationships. Introduces values identification and assertive communication role-plays. Encourages developmentally appropriate goal setting and self-expression.	These strategies support the development of a clearer I-P by helping the student distinguish thoughts, feelings, and values from relational pressure, fostering autonomous functioning within relationships.
EC	Student suppresses emotions to avoid burdening caregivers and minimizes personal distress.	Builds rapport and normalizes emotions to create a safe relational context. Uses journaling prompts to externalize emotions without avoiding them. Encourages verbal labeling of feelings during sessions.	These actions reduce emotional cutoff by promoting expression in a contained, nonthreatening school-based setting, allowing engagement without overwhelm.
FO	Student acts as messenger between parents and assumes a stabilizing role in the family system.	Names triangulation in age-appropriate language and clarifies role boundaries. Collaborates with caregivers, with consent, to reduce the child’s involvement in parental communication. Promotes independent coping and decision-making skills within the school setting.	These actions address fusion by reducing role reversal and reinforcing appropriate generational boundaries, supporting differentiation without disrupting family relationships.

Note. ER = emotional reactivity, IP = I-position, EC = emotional cutoff, FO = fusion with others. Table 2 aligns with Table 1 by linking counselor behaviors to the recommended responses, reinforcing differentiation as skill-based, school-appropriate practice as opposed to insight-oriented family therapy (Kerr & Bowen, 1988; Skowron & Friedlander, 1998; Skowron & Schmitt, 2003).

Family Engagement and Community Collaboration

Family education is a critical extension of school counseling practice when supporting students affected by high-conflict separation or divorce (ASCA, 2025). While school counselors do not provide family therapy, they are well positioned to offer preventive outreach that helps caregivers understand how emotional reactivity, boundary diffusion, and triangulation can unintentionally intensify student distress. Brief workshops or informational sessions with parents focused on maintaining clear adult boundaries, minimizing children's involvement in parental conflict, and supporting consistent routines can reinforce differentiation-supportive environments without exceeding counselors' ethical scope (Čepukienė & Neophytou, 2024). Such efforts align with trauma-informed and systems-oriented practice by addressing upstream relational dynamics that shape students' emotional functioning in school (ASCA, 2025; McLain et al., 2025).

Effective school and family communication practices further reduce systemic strain on students navigating divided households. Counselors can establish structured communication norms that limit role reversal, such as clarifying that school-related concerns are communicated directly between adults, not through the child (ASCA, 2025). When appropriate and with consent, counselors may provide guidance on parallel parenting strategies that prioritize predictability and emotional neutrality in school interactions (O'Hara & Cohen, 2024). These practices help the school function as a consistent, structured context that reduces students' perceived responsibility for managing adult relationships and supports more adaptive emotional regulation (Savitz-Romer et al., 2021).

Finally, coordination with community mental health resources is essential when family conflict exceeds what can be addressed through school-based support alone. School counselors serve as gatekeepers by identifying and referring students whose presentations suggest chronic exposure to extreme emotional reactivity or impaired parental functioning, and collaborating with community providers, family courts, or school-linked mental health services allows counselors to maintain appropriate boundaries while ensuring continuity of care (Warren et al., 2024). Viewed through a Bowenian lens, this coordinated approach supports differentiation at multiple systemic levels, reinforcing the school's role as a protective and regulating context while connecting families to resources capable of addressing deeper relational patterns (Kerr & Bowen, 1988).

Professional Implications and Recommendations

School counselors require coherent, systems-informed frameworks to support students effectively and to sustain their own professional functioning amid the relational complexity of high-conflict family contexts. Building from the case illustration, intervention mapping, and family education strategies, we have designed a professional development module for immediate, real-world implementation. By positioning differentiation-informed practice as both systemic and school-appropriate, this approach enables counselors to move beyond symptom management while maintaining ethical boundaries. Extending these efforts through caregiver education and community collaboration further reinforces the school as a regulating and protective context that supports student adjustment amid ongoing family stress.

Training, Supervision, and Professional Development Implications

School counselors are often the first professionals to encounter students experiencing distress related to parental separation or divorce, yet counselors may have received limited

formal preparation in family systems theory. This deficit may lead to an underdeveloped understanding of how relational dynamics may drive behavioral changes and academic disruption (Paylo, 2011). Family and systems theory remains inconsistently integrated across counselor education programs, despite its relevance to conceptual competence and effective practice, underscoring the need for applied, systems-informed training models (Falkenstien et al., 2024; Schmidt et al., 2025).

The preceding case illustration and intervention mapping demonstrate the practical, ethically appropriate utility of DoS frameworks within school settings. To ensure effective and sustainable implementation of such strategies, however, requires their inclusion in counselor training, supervision, and professional development. DoS is more than a client characteristic; it is also an effective mechanism for increasing school counselor competency. Without sufficient differentiation, counselors may experience increased emotional reactivity, feel pressured to side with one caregiver, or become triangulated into family conflict (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). Training that explicitly addresses counselors' own regulation, boundary maintenance, and capacity to maintain an I-position is essential (Paylo, 2011).

Preparation should help practitioners recognize when relational pressure rather than professional judgment shapes their responses. This awareness supports clear decision-making, consistent communication practices, and clear delineation of ethical roles, particularly in schools where counselors manage large caseloads with limited time (ASCA, 2025). Emphasizing counselor differentiation aligns with trauma-informed practice by reducing burnout risk and supporting reflective as opposed to reactive intervention (Dollarhide & Saginak, 2017; McLain et al., 2025).

Supervision plays a critical role in reinforcing systems-informed practice. Supervisory conversations should address emotional processing as well as technique and compliance and examination of how family dynamics, school culture, and personal stressors intersect in complex cases (Minor & Duchac, 2023). Supervisors who incorporate differentiation-based reflection can help counselors identify patterns of fusion, cutoff, or over-functioning that may emerge when supporting students from high-conflict homes. Targeted training modules that translate Bowenian concepts into school-based decision-making are likely to be most effective because they can help counselors recognize early warning signs of systemic distress and respond to triangulation while maintaining their own differentiation (Falkenstien et al., 2024; Paylo, 2011). These approaches are particularly relevant in districts with limited access to external mental health resources, where school counselors fill both preventive and supportive roles (Warren et al., 2024).

A Differentiation-Informed Professional Development Model

To support practical implementation, a brief professional development module can be incorporated into in-service training, district workshops, or state association programming. The module should include an overview of DoS and its relevance to school counseling, followed by case-based discussions of common scenarios involving parental conflict (Dack & Merlin-Knoblich, 2023). Counselors should learn to identify emotional reactivity, boundary challenges, and opportunities for differentiation-supportive interventions at the student, classroom, and family-communication levels. Interactive components, such as role-plays and guided reflection exercises, provide practice for maintaining an I-position while responding to caregiver concerns or student distress (Paylo, 2011).

The module should be designed for adaptability across grade levels, school contexts, and community settings (ASCA, 2025), delivered in a 60- to 90-minute in-service training that

combines didactic instruction, vignette analysis, and guided reflection (Falkenstien et al., 2024). Expected outcomes include greater counselor confidence in recognizing triangulation, more consistent boundary-setting in communication with caregivers, and increased use of differentiation-supportive interventions in daily practice. Such modules integrate easily into existing professional development structures without additional staffing or resources (Minor & Duchac, 2023).

Future Directions for Practice and Research

Future researchers should examine the impact of differentiation-informed training on counselor confidence, decision-making, and student outcomes. Particular attention to mechanisms such as triangulation and co-parenting quality, which mediate the link between parental DoS and child adjustment, especially in regions with high rates of family transitions and economic stressors, are necessary (Čepukienė & Neophytou, 2024; Johnston et al., 2025; Karhina et al., 2023). At the policy level, counselor education programs and state associations should embed family systems theory more deeply within preservice curricula and continuing education requirements (Falkenstien et al., 2024). Prioritizing practical, systems-informed preparation will better equip school counselors to support students navigating parental separation while maintaining ethical boundaries (Paylo, 2011). Framing DoS as both a conceptual lens and a counselor competency may enable school counselors to respond effectively to complex family dynamics and support students' wellbeing amid ongoing relational stress (Schmidt et al., 2025).

Conclusion

This translation of Bowen family systems theory and DoS into practical, school-based counseling strategies addresses student anxiety and adjustment difficulties associated with parental separation or divorce. School counselors need coherent, evidence-informed frameworks

to guide ethical and effective intervention, particularly given the well-documented impact of family disruption on students' emotional, behavioral, and academic functioning (Amato, 2010; D'Onofrio & Emery, 2019; Kelly & Emery, 2003). DoS offers a unifying conceptual lens for linking parental coping patterns to observable student behaviors in school (Calatrava et al., 2022). By operationalizing the four DoS subscales and connecting parental emotional functioning to common student presentations and corresponding counselor responses, we provide practitioners with a practical, real-time translation tool.

Integrating family systems theory with developmentally appropriate, prevention-oriented interventions enables school counselors to move beyond symptom management toward systemic understanding that fosters student resilience, emotional regulation, and academic engagement (Titelman, 2014). Although previous researchers provided a strong conceptual foundation for applying family systems theory to children's experiences of parental separation, structured school-based tools and differentiation-informed training models remain limited (Falkenstien et al., 2024). We addressed that gap by weaving together theory, empirical research, and applied practice within the daily realities of school counseling.

By positioning DoS as both a conceptual framework and a professional competency, this work strengthens the school's role as a stabilizing system amid ongoing family stress and advances more ethically grounded, systemically informed school counseling practice (Schmidt et al., 2025). Although developed with the needs of school counselors in Alabama and the Southeastern United States in mind, these approaches are readily adaptable for counselor preparation, supervision, and professional development nationwide.

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